

To Participate or Not to Participate? Selecting the Right Participant Profile for Thermal and Visual Comfort Studies

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ABSTRACT

Energy consumption reduction in buildings poses great challenges to modern societies in which maintaining thermal and visual comfort is occupants' primary desire in indoor environments. In order to determine satisfaction levels of occupants, surveys are widely used to obtain feedback with respect to thermal and visual perceptions. However, low participation to the surveys might cause misleading results, and, thus, result in defining wrong strategies to maintain occupant comfort in buildings. Therefore, factors that affect participation to the surveys have to be analyzed so that the surveys can be distributed to the most responsive profile. This study aims at investigating the relationship between factors related to participant profile (gender, age group, energy awareness level and the number of energy activities attended) and survey participation ratio. A survey was conducted in an office building in France between December 19, 2016 and September 25, 2017. A total of 93 occupants participated in the study. The relationship between participation ratio and the occupant related factors were analyzed via Kruskal-Wallis tests. The results show that the energy awareness level has a statistically significant effect on the survey participation ratio whereas gender and age group have not a significant effect on the survey participation ratio. Therefore, this result is a proof that the energy awareness levels of occupants have to be increased in order to reach higher participation ratios.

Author Keywords

Survey participation; gender; age group; energy awareness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, maintaining satisfactory indoor environments for users are essential to both facility managers and building owners since it effects the interaction of users with building systems, which in turn could increase the energy consumption significantly. It should be noted that each individual has his/her own requirements to feel comfortable and that certain physical needs have to be met in indoor environments. When these criteria are met, then the

occupant can be described as comfortable [11]. In addition, a number of scientific studies have clearly shown that the performance capacity, job satisfaction, job enjoyment and health are directly affected by the comfort offered by the physical work environment [5]. In particular, thermal and visual comforts form an important part of the physical environment. Many studies have shown that the perception of thermal comfort has a great impact on the satisfaction with the workplace [7, 10, 15, 16]. In addition, visual comfort is crucial for user satisfaction since light has a positive influence on health and well-being due to a higher level of lighting.

Today, building systems rely on the standards to define occupant comfort ranges [12]. In particular, ISO 7730 [9] and ASHRAE 55 [1] standards are widely used to define ranges for thermal comfort whereas ISO 16817 [8] is used for visual comfort. However; these standards do not reflect the preference of users, and, thus, do not ensure user satisfaction [3, 4, 6, 13, 14, 16]. Subsequently, occupants interact with building systems to ensure their comfort levels, which in turn lead to increased energy consumption in real situations. Therefore, occupants' satisfaction and preferences need to be considered as a complementary source of information in building management systems. In order to determine satisfaction, and, thus, comfort levels of occupants, surveys are widely used to provide feedback with respect to thermal and visual perceptions. However, low participation to the surveys might cause misleading results, and, thus, wrong strategies to maintain comfort in buildings. Therefore, factors that affect participation to the surveys have to be analyzed so that the surveys can be distributed to the most responsive profile.

This study aims at investigating the relationship between factors related to participant profile (gender, age group, energy awareness level and the number of energy activities attended) and survey participation ratio. The following sections present the materials and methodology, and then provide results and discussion.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

This study considers the general research question of survey response ratios along four factors related to participant profile: gender, age group, energy awareness level and the number of energy activities attended. It should be noted that other sociodemographic parameters (i.e. income, education level) could not be included in this study due to ethical concerns.

2.1 Test Building

The study was conducted in 'Challenger' site, an office building with 68 000 m² and the headquarters of Bouygues Construction located in Guyancourt, to the West of Paris, France. Regarding the climatic conditions, summers are warm and mild with no dry season. It receives approximately equal rainfall every month during the year and the average temperature of all months is lower than 22°C. The hottest month is July, when the maximum temperature is about 24°C whereas the coldest month is January, when the minimum temperature is 1°C in average.

The energy sources used by the building are ground-source, photovoltaic, thermal solar, electricity and a thermal generator (security). Photovoltaic panels (dual PV-T solar panels on roofs) produce part of the electricity necessary for the operation of the buildings. The energies naturally present in the ground (ground-source) and air (air-source) are primary energy sources for the heating and air conditioning of the buildings. Lighting system of the buildings consist of fluorescent lamp tube and LED.

Regarding the organization of the spaces, there are small rooms, open space offices and meeting rooms. On the other hand, the type of occupation in buildings is non-permanent. The buildings involve different types of users: Employees, energy managers, facility managers and visitors. The building is generally occupied between 8:00 am and 7:00 pm during the weekdays.

The survey is conducted on the second floor of the building (Figure 1) with a total area of 1919 m². 93 employees were occupying the zone at the time when the questionnaire was sent.

Figure 1. Survey distribution zone on the second floor.

2.2 Survey

An online questionnaire was designed and distributed repeatedly via email to building occupants in order to assess the thermal and visual comfort conditions provided by the building to its occupants as well as to extract information about participant profiles including gender, age group, energy awareness level and energy related activities. Responses of the survey provide an indication as to the performance of the lighting, heating, ventilation, and air conditioning systems while providing direction for making improvements to building systems in an attempt to provide a continual comfortable environment for building occupants.

2.3 Participants

The survey was distributed to 2 groups of occupants. The first group consisting of 33 occupants were involved in the study between December 19, 2016 and September 25, 2017 whereas the second group consisting of 60 occupants were involved between July 07, 2017 and September 25, 2017. The questionnaire was distributed 20 times once every two weeks. Therefore, the frequency of distribution was the same for both periods. A total of 93 occupants participated in the study. It should be noted that the aim of including two different groups is to have a large sample size, and, thus, no comparison is provided between two groups within this study. A similar analysis can be conducted at a larger scale (i.e. municipality); however, it was not possible to recruit people at this scale. The statistical significance between females and males as well as 5 age groups (18-24; 25-34; 35-44, 45-54 and 55-64) were assessed. The majority of participants (31%) were in the age range of 45-54 and the percentage of the female subjects was 67%. Figure 2 shows the distribution of participants with respect to gender and age group.

Figure 2. Distribution of participants with respect to (a) gender (b) age group.

The majority of participants (41%) evaluated their energy efficiency awareness as ‘medium’ whereas only 3% of participants evaluated their energy efficiency awareness as ‘very high’. Moreover, only 3% of participants specified that they participated to 5 energy activities such as conferences, symposiums etc. The majority of participants (52%) specified that they didn’t participate in any energy related activities. It should be noted that since there is no permanent occupancy in these kinds of buildings and due to privacy issues, the participation of the same people was not scrutinized in the tests. Figure 3 shows the distribution of participants with respect to energy awareness level and the number of energy activities they attended.

Figure 3. Distribution of participants with respect to (a) energy awareness level (b) the number of energy activities.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data analyses were conducted to investigate the possible effects and the magnitude of participant profile on survey participation ratio by using SPSS (version 22.0 for Windows) software. In particular, the analyses were carried out to understand if there is a significant effect of gender, age group, energy awareness level and the number of energy activities on survey participation ratio. In order to determine the applicable significance test, normality tests were conducted to the data based on the survey participation ratio. After the analyses of normality tests, non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was selected to understand whether survey participation ratio, differed based on participant profile. It should be noted that the probability values for calculated H values (test statistics) were estimated by chi-square distribution in Kruskal-Wallis test. The significance of the data analysis was determined as 95% ($p \leq 0.05$). Finally, the Mann-Whitney U tests were conducted to investigate the data groups which cause the statistical significance.

3 RESULTS

The results of Shapiro-Wilk normality tests are given in Table 1. The results of normality tests show that the survey participation ratios are not normally distributed for gender and energy awareness level since all p -values are smaller than significance level (0.05). It should be noted that if one of the subgroups in a parameter is not normally distributed, then Kruskal-Wallis test needs to be selected for further

analyses as in the case of age group (55-64) and the number of energy activities (3 and 5 activities). Therefore, non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test is selected for significance for all factors.

Factor	Variable	Test statistics	p-value
Gender	Female	0.736	0.000
	Male	0.707	0.000
Age Group	18-24	0.600	0.029
	25-34	0.753	0.000
	34-44	0.679	0.000
	45-54	0.854	0.000
	55-64	0.853	0.121
Energy awareness level	Very low	0.474	0.000
	Low	0.832	0.000
	Medium	0.711	0.000
	High	0.787	0.000
	Very high	0.750	0.000
The number of energy activities	0	0.729	0.000
	1	0.776	0.000
	2	0.704	0.007
	3	0.789	0.195
	5	0.750	0.637

Table 1. Normality test results for survey participation rate.

The results of Kruskal-Wallis tests are shown in Table 2. The results show that the survey participation ratio differed only based on energy awareness level of participants ($p=0.007<0.05$). In other words, the energy awareness levels of participant have a statistically significant effect on the survey participation ratio whereas gender, age group and the number of energy related activities do have not a significant effect on the survey participation ratio.

The results of Mann-Whitney U tests are presented in Table 3. It should be noted that the bolded values indicate the statistical significance, which in other words indicate whether there is a statistical difference between two variables or not. The results show that 3 of the Mann-Whitney U tests' values of "very high" energy awareness level are smaller than the confidence level of 0.05. This result indicates that the effect of the participants whose energy awareness level is 'very high' is dominant on the survey participation ratio with respect to other energy awareness levels. The effects of the "high" energy awareness level are not notable on the participation since it has p-values higher than the confidence level of 0.05.

	Test Statistics			
	Chi-square	df	p	
Gender	0.030	1	0.473	Not significant
Age group	8.080	4	0.262	Not significant
Energy awareness level	12.997	4	0.007	Significant
The number of energy related activities	1.874	4	0.163	Not Significant

Table 2. Kruskal-Wallis tests results for the survey participation ratio

		Energy awareness level				
		Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high
Energy awareness level	Very low	X				
	Low	0.014	X			
	Medium	0.339	0.022	X		
	High	0.186	0.386	0.470	X	
	Very High	0.111	0.003	0.030	0.007	X

Table 3. Results of Mann-Whitney U tests for the survey participation ratio of energy awareness level

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, a survey related to thermal and visual comfort was conducted in an office building between December 19, 2016 and September 25, 2017. A total of 93 occupants were involved in the study. Statistical analyses including Shapiro-Wilk normality tests, Kruskal-Wallis tests and Mann Whitney U tests were conducted to investigate the relationship between factors related to participant profile (gender, age group, energy awareness level and the number of energy activities attended) and survey participation ratio. The results show that the energy awareness levels of participant have a statistically significant effect on the survey participation ratio whereas gender, age group and the number of energy related activities do have not a significant effect on the survey participation ratio. In particular, the effect of the participants whose energy awareness level is 'very high' is dominant on the survey participation ratio. This result could be interpreted as the participants whose energy awareness levels are "very high" could be willing to contribute to these kinds of studies. In order to increase the participation ratios of other participants, information about the survey and its relation to energy consumption could be designed in a way that energy awareness levels of participants could be increased. Providing information about the impact that their responses would have on the energy efficiency as well as presenting figures on the relevant surveys and their outcomes might be solutions to increase the participation ratio. In addition, the motivation of occupants could be increased by giving feedback on the responses. Occupants' participation ratios and how their responses are used for energy efficiency purposes might also affect their energy awareness levels, and, thus, their participation ratios in the next distribution.

The limitation of this study is the sampling frame, which is considered in an office building. The building is occupied by professionals with at least a bachelor degree, and, thus, it might be significantly different from the general population of other buildings (i.e. residential). In addition, the availability of socio-demographic records of all members of the sampling frame is limited to aggregate information about gender, age group, energy awareness level and energy related activities. Future studies can focus on investigating the significance of other socio-demographic as well as socio-economic factors such as educational background, job position and annual income. In addition, similar studies can be conducted in other types of buildings including residential and industrial buildings.

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